

Avicore

- Renewable aviation bio-fuel derived from microbial fermentation of biomass.
- High energy ether compounds group compatible with jet engine.
- Pending patent application: PA 2010 00471
- TOP 3 in Venture Cup Cleantech 2010.

Non sustainable aviation

- Single commercial flight from Standsted to Rome emits 27 tonnes CO₂.
- 344.109 tonnes CO₂ is emitted from European aviation industry a day.
- The figures are rising...

Resources are scarce

- Current oil reserves sufficient for next 40 years.
- Alternative solutions:
 - Electricity, bio-ethanol – not enough power,
 - Fuel crops – low compatibility with jet engine,
 - Hydrogen, cryogenic, etc. – early stage research.

Avi-fuel value proposition

CO₂ neutral

Renewable

High energy density

Cheaper

and

Jet engine compatible:

- Operational parameters
- No alteration of motors
- Existing fuel distributors

The market is gigantic

- 208.000.000 tones fuel consumed each year (2005).
- Potential for substitution:
 - Current – 25%,
 - Future – possibly 100%.